

Local Government Administration and the Challenges of Bureaucratic Professionalism in Nigeria: A Study of Transition Committee in Local Government Councils in Anambra State (2015 to 2022)

Dr. Victor E. Udegbumam (JP) FCPA, FIMS, FCMC, CMC, IMS
*Political Science Department, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam
Igbariam/ Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria*

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Abstract:

The democratic essence of governance is expressed and most often experienced at the grass root. The instrument of government that conveys this is the local government through sound bureaucratic experts. But it appears that the introduction of the Transition Committee has encouraged the rescinding of bureaucratic professionalism in local government administration in Nigeria. This paper becomes imperatively tasked with ascertaining the impact of Transition Committee on bureaucratic professionalism in local government councils in Anambra State. Following this, two research questions were adopted to guide the study. First, does the introduction of Transition Committee down played bureaucratic professionalism in local government administration in Anambra

State? Secondly, what factors attributed to Transition Committee are responsible for low performance of local government administration in Anambra State? Data were primarily sourced and complimented with secondary source precisely academic journals and government gazettes. Bureaucratic theory was used as relevant tool of analysis. From the study, it was discovered that majority of the members of Transition Committee in local government councils are people of poor academic qualifications with little or no bureaucratic knowledge. These personalities exhibit administrative rascality in their dealings with career civil servants and bureaucratic ignorance in the discharge of their functions. These have adversely affected bureaucratic professionalism in local government administration in Anambra State. Hence, the study recommends total administrative and financial independence in the local government councils by abrogating transition committee in local government.

Keywords: *Local Government Administration, Bureaucratic Professionalism, Transition Committee, Administrative rascality, bureaucratic ignorance.*

Introduction

The Local government administration in Nigeria has a long history since 1972 and found basis in the Reform of 1976 but the fundamental essence of this tier of government in addressing the welfare of the people at the grass root remains a great concern. Provision of basic amenities and

social infrastructures are fundamental to the sustenance of the people at the grass root hence, Local Government role in this regard becomes imperative and central. In this line of thought, the local government fundamentally is required to provide rural roads, build markets, health care centers, burial grounds, drainages, motor parks,

build primary schools, among others but it appears presently that the local government councils are merely administrative structures without organic life. Explanation of which has elicited several intellectual attentions to which some are aligned to total usurp of the local government autonomy by the state government on the ground that it is the creation of the latter. However, the knowledge of the fact that the local government remains a tier of government precisely the third tier of government with defined statutory functions as contained in chapter four schedule (1) of the 1999 constitution (as amended) of Federal Republic of Nigeria has continued to be trampled upon with impunity by the state government and has further exacerbated the situation with the introduction of Transition Committee System in Anambra State.

The introduction of Transition Committee System in the 21 Local Government Councils of Anambra State seems to have adversely affected and down played on bureaucratic professionalism in the state. It is in the light of the foregoing that this paper is tasked with the responsibility of examining the impact of Transition Committee System on bureaucratic professionalism in Local Government Administration in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Section 7 (1) of 1999 constitution (as amended) provide that: “The system of Local government by democratically elected local government councils is under this constitution guaranteed; and accordingly, the government of every state shall, subject to section 8 of this constitution, ensure their existence under a law which provides for the establishment, structure, composition, finance and functions of such councils”. This infers that the law relating to local government creation would be made by the State Houses of Assembly. The legal framework does not see local government as a third tier of government but merely recognizes local government as an appendage of the state government where the latter enjoys absolute discretion over the former (Abdulhamid and Chima, 2015). This inherent contradiction

provides ample opportunities for state government to easily manipulate the local government system in which Anambra State is not an exception.

In frantic effort to utilize all available constitutional privileges granted to the state government and to ensure its exertive control of the local government in the state, Anambra State government has continued to relentlessly inaugurate Transition Committee members in the 21 local government councils of the state. This development over the years has not facilitated any tangible development stride in the state neither has it enhance the sense of political inclusiveness of the people at the grass root. Rather the feelers have indicated clearly that the Transition Committee system appears to be an administrative structure designed by the state government to effectively manipulate and exert perpetual control of the finances of the local government. This is further made pellucid in the recruitment of the members of this committee, their academic qualification and their religious dependence on the state Governor’s consent for the discharge of their statutory functions. This has unequivocally hampered the administrative advancement of the local government councils of the state.

It is against this back drop that the thrust of this paper becomes central to interrogate the impact of transition committee system on bureaucratic professionalism in local government administration using Transition Committee System of Anambra State as a test case.

Research Questions

Extrapolating from the prevailing research problem, the understated research questions are adopted to guide the study;

1. Does the introduction of Transition Committee down played bureaucratic professionalism in local government councils in Anambra State?
2. What factors attributed to Transition Committee are responsible for low performance of local government system in Anambra State?

Objectives of the Study

This paper is primarily anchored on determining the impact of Transition Committee System on local government administration in Anambra State. On the basis of this the study attempts;

1. To ascertain how the introduction of Transition Committee has down played bureaucratic professionalism in the local government.
2. To determine factors responsible for low performance of local government system in Anambra State.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Local Government and Local Government Administration

Local government is a generic term for the lowest tiers of public administration within a particular sovereign state (Wikipedia, 2011). This particular usage of the word government refers specifically to a level of administration that is both geographically located and with defined jurisdiction. Whereas Christian (2022) opined that it is the government of a specific local area constituting a subdivision of a major political unit. Disagreeing with the above explanations, Sikander (2015) argued that local government is an agent of social change which cannot be identified with a sovereign government in terms of security, defence, bank rates, taxation, etc. These perceptions have construed the concept of local government in the light of change agent in provision of social amenities and a sub unit of a national government. However, in the context of this paper local government is perceived as a legal entity that is formed with the aim of delivering local and communal public services in a particular geographical location whose decision making body is acceded through free elections and has administrative and financial autonomy.

In a different parlance, local government administration refers to the administration of a community by a body which is not responsible to the local people but to those who appoint

them to govern (Shamsuddin and Ibrahim, 2012). While Abba et al (2007) agreed that local government administration is a process of governance by local inhabitants freely elected to carry out programmes to improve the well being of the people at the grass root. It is best to hold that it is the whole process of decision making at the local government level or selected persons by central or state governments to carry out certain functions for the benefits of the local inhabitants. This perception has been violently refuted particularly in the area of selected persons by the state government to prevail over the affairs of the local government. This position is backed by the provisions of section 7 (1) and sub-section (2) (a and b) of 1979 constitution which provides that the system of local government by democratically elected local government councils is under this constitution guaranteed; and accordingly, the government of every state shall ensure their existence under a law which provides for the establishment, structure, composition, finance and functions of such councils. In same vain, Edict No. 9 of 1976 A.S.N. parts ii, iii (5.5) and b, part IV and part V are on local government areas, alteration of areas of authority, establishment of local governments, local government headquarters and composition of councils and elections (Anambra State Government, 1976 in Mbaebie, (2020).

According to Mbaebie (2020), section (1) of the constitution basically gave two important aspects of the 1976 reforms guaranteed by its provision. First, it sought to preserve the political character of the local government council as representative bodies in the first few lines of this section. The constitution went further than the 1976 reforms did by not leaving room for nominated members as the local government law of all the states. Despite constitutional provisions for the establishment of local government councils (democratically elected councils) and not appointment of Transition or Management Committee, the Governors have continued to flout and disregard it. Dissolution of councils and dismissal of elected councilors by the state Governors have become more of a routine. This

development indicates arrogant disregard to the constitutional provisions and reckless abuse of the legal framework establishing the local government as the third tier of government.

Functions of Local Government in Nigeria

The local government system comprises of democratically elected local government councils which are equally guaranteed under the 1999 constitution section 7 (as amended). Section 7 of the 1999 constitution (as amended) provides for the functions of a local government council under the Fourth Schedule. This schedule tends to derive mainly from the Basic and Constitutional Transition Provisions (Decree 15 of 1987). Thus, the functions of local governments are categorized into:

1. The Exclusive List; and
2. The Concurrent List.

The Exclusive List of functions are those functions that are solely performed by local governments. While the concurrent list of functions are those that the local government performs in collaboration with State and Federal Governments. The State and/or Federal Government can also perform these functions on behalf of local governments until local governments are in a position to perform such functions.

Fourth schedule (1) of the 1999 constitution rails out the following as the functions of the local government council;

1. The consideration and the making of recommendations to a state commission on economic planning or any similar body on;
2. The economic development of the state, particularly in so far as the areas of authority of the council and of the state are affected, and
3. Proposals made by the said commission or body;
4. Collection of rates, radio and television license;
5. Establishment and maintenance of cemeteries, burial grounds and homes for the destitute or infirm;

6. Licensing of bicycles, trucks (other than mechanically propelled trucks), canoes, wheel barrows and carts;
7. Establishment, maintenance of and regulation of slaughter houses, slaughter slabs, markets, motor parks and public conveniences;
8. Construction and maintenance of roads, streets, street lightings, drains and other public highways, parks, gardens, open spaces or such public facilities as may be prescribed from time to time by the House of Assembly of a state;
9. Naming of roads and streets and numbering of houses;
10. Provision and maintenance of public conveniences, sewage and refuse disposal;
11. Registration of all births, deaths and marriages;
12. Assessment of privately owned houses or tenements for the purpose of levying such rates as may be proscribed by the House of Assembly of a state; and
13. Control and regulation of:
 - a. Out-door advertising and hoarding,
 - b. Movement and keeping of pets of all description,
 - c. Shops and Kiosks,
 - d. Restaurants, bakeries and other places for sale,
 - e. Laundries, and
 - f. Licensing, regulation and control of the sale of Liquor.

Under section 2 of the Fourth Schedule, the functions of a local government council shall include participation of such council in the government of a state with respect to the following:

1. The provision and maintenance of primary, adult and vocational education;
2. The development of agriculture and natural resources, other than the exploitation of minerals;

3. The provision and maintenance of health services; and
4. Such other functions as may be conferred on a local government council by the House of Assembly of the State.

Again, Local government administration also involves informative functions such as enlightenment, development projects, administration, democratic and leadership initiative and maintenance of peace, Law and order in the Locality (Awotokun, 2005 in Shamasuddi and Ibrahim, 2014).

Empirical Review of Bureaucratic Professionalism and Transition Committee in Local Government

The concept of bureaucratic professionalism was first conceived by Weber. When Weber conceived of the concept of a bureaucratic organization, he had in mind the intended consequences of systematic, orderly, predictable organizational behaviors. Such intended consequence of organizational behaviors cannot be expected from a purely bureaucratic organization. These can be expected only when professionalism coexists with bureaucracy. According to Velayutham (1994), the Weberian type of organization with a high degree of both professionalism and bureaucracy could be termed bureaucratic professionalism or professional bureaucracy. Whereas, Suzuki and Demircioglu (2017), empirically posited that bureaucratic professionalism is merit-based recruitment and internally recruited senior officials rather than political appointees or political network-based recruitment. Aligning with this thought, Egeberg (2012 in Suzuki and Demircioglu, 2017) argued that modern bureaucratic structures bring about more professionalism which obviously influence social outcomes. From his study, it was observed that in a meritocratic recruitment system, public sector organizations select competent and skillful bureaucrats than they can in a politicized one. Bureaucratic professionalism encourages recruitment of best possible personnel which is logical means of filling positions with best qualified personnel (Peters, 2010). In contrast, a lack of professional public administration

reduces chances of hiring employees who are knowledgeable and expert in policy areas with higher commitment to their jobs. Thus, bureaucratic professionalism encourages expertise, long-term perspective of efficiency and less influence of political patronage and interests as it is seen in transition committee recruitment and modus of operation in the local government system.

Assessing the interface between bureaucratic professionalism and transition committee in the local government system, Okafor and Orjinta (2010 in Mbaebie, 2020) argued that Transition Committee (Caretaker Committee) is antithetical to bureaucratic professionalism. An empirical study of Onitsha North Local Government Caretaker Committee revealed that there is a unanimous agreement on the lack of impact of caretaker committee on improving the living condition of the area. The Committee members lamented that they only receive salary at the end of the month which is paid only when the governor approves it. From 2000 to 2020, Local governments in Anambra State did not witness any serious development. This colossal failure of the committee gears to the fact that they are at the mercy of the state government.

In today's reality, no local government engages in any form of developmental projects without the approval and financing of the state government. The adverse impact of transition committee on bureaucratic professionalism in the local government is more pronounced in social realities. This according to Mbaebie (2020), has to do with the quality of relationship that exists between the caretaker committee members and career civil servants. The relationship however was such that the committee members are perceived as the express representatives of the Governor who can sack at will the civil servants at the snap of their fingers. This inherent fear hinders the civil servants from confronting the committee members even when they abuse the oath of their offices. This has also resulted in total usurp of the bureaucratic statutory duties of the civil servants by politicians who are novice to administrative activities and as such rescind bureaucratic

professionalism in the local government system of Anambra State.

Gap in Knowledge

From the extent literature, it was observed that full intellectual attention was given to the concept of local government and local government administration with much emphasis on the constitutional provisions on the establishment and statutory functions of the local government as contained in schedule 4, section 7(1) and (2) of 1999 constitution (as amended).

Again, on the central issue of the paper which revolves around bureaucratic professionalism and Transition Committee in local government, scholars have argued that local government remains a bureaucratic organization and it is controlled by administrative structure with defined hierarchy of authority (Velayutham, 1994, Suzuki and Demircioglu, 2017 and Egeberg, 2012). In all of these, little was said on the Transition Committee's impact on the local government administration in Anambra State.

It is against this backdrop that this paper becomes expedient to the extent at which it attempts to ascertain the impact of Transition Committee on bureaucratic professionalism in local government system in Anambra State.

Theoretical Framework

The basic thrust of this paper is anchored on ascertaining the extent to which the introduction of Transition Committee has downplayed bureaucratic professionalism in local government system in Nigeria. In the light of this, bureaucratic theory is adopted as a relevant framework of analysis in attempt to offer more explanations in the operation and administration of the local government in this regard.

The Chief proponent of bureaucratic theory is Max Weber. He construed bureaucratic theory in the light of structure and administrative process of organization. The term bureaucracy means the rules and regulations, processes, procedures, patterns, etc, that are formulated to reduce the complexity of organization's functioning. In this regard, bureaucratic organization is one that has a hierarchy of authority, specialized work force,

standardized principles, rules and regulations, trained administrative personnel, etc, as the local government institution is one of such organizations argued by Weber in which it is expected that individual performance is judged through the role-based activity and promotions serves as motivation to individuals with outstanding performance.

Extrapolating from the above, one fact is pellucid about Max Weber bureaucratic theory and that is an organization that is rule-based, defined hierarchy and line of communication clearly spelt. Placing this side by side with the prevailing situation in the local government today in Anambra State, one can say without fear of contradiction that the local government system in Anambra State is a blatant disregard to bureaucratic principles. It is a situation where the Transition Committee Chairmen award contracts without the involvement of the bureaucrats (HLGAs – Heads of Local Government Administration) provided the State government approves such contracts. It is also observed that some Chairmen sign Identification Certificates and Marriage Certificate which are statutory documents with impunity at the detriment of administrative professionalism thereby encouraging administrative rascality and bureaucratic ignorance climaxing into total usurp of the relevance of the local government as a tier of government. Again, what seems to have worsened this is the personality of individuals who make up the membership of the Transition Committee and the criteria of their selection which is totally political other than merit-based. Majority of them are not educated. Most of whom cannot write except for the Chairmen some of whom are educated but not trained with administrative skills hence the system appears a mockery of bureaucratic professionalism. Rules and regulations upon which local government is established are blatantly flouted with reckless abandon. The interest is not service delivery to the people at the grass root except for paying allegiance to the Governor who appointed them. There is no connection between the Transition Committee and administrative network of the system as all channels of administrative communication is

between the Transition Committee Chairman and the State Government. This becomes clearly an opposite of what Max Weber propagated as bureaucratic organization and consequently bureaucratic professionalism becoming a mirage in the local government system in Anambra State.

Research Design

The paper adopted a quasi-scientific survey approach which is clearly descriptive survey. It sourced for academic publications on the subject and identified both online and offline resources that address the topic.

Method of Data Collection

The study relied both on primary and secondary data. This was due to the nature of subject under study. Under the primary method of data collection, the study employed a structured questionnaire instrument and the secondary data was clearly sourced through online and journal publications on similar subject.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is the staff of the three local government councils randomly selected from the three senatorial zones. These local government councils are identified below with specific staff strength of each local government council as supplied by respective local government Heads of Personnel Management.

Table 1. Local Government Council Staff Strength

S/N	Names	Staff Strength
1	Idemili North Local Government Council (Anambra Central)	601
2	Onitsha South (Anambra North)	478
3	Orumba South (Anambra South)	277
Total		1356

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Sample and Sampling Technique

In consideration of the size of the study area and population of 1356 representing the population size of the three selected local government councils, sample survey technique was used. Out of which a sample of 309 was drawn from the population of study. The size of the sample was determined using Taro Yamane's formular. The formular is as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where;

- n = Sample size
- N = Total number of staff strength of the three local government councils
- I = Constant variable
- e = Degree of error (at 0.05)

Hence, the sample size is calculated as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1356}{1+1356(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1356}{1+(1356 \cdot 0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1356}{1+3.39}$$

$$n = \frac{1356}{4.39}$$

$$n = 308.88 \quad \text{approximately } 309$$

$$n = 309$$

Decision Point is made at (SA) + (A) = ACCEPTED (4.0 TO 5) and (D) + (SD) + (U) = REJECTED (1.0 TO 3). The distribution of the sample among the selected local government councils is determined as outlined below;

Idemili North Local Government Council

$$= n^1 = \frac{\sum(x \cdot y)}{N}$$

$$n^1 = \frac{601 \cdot 309}{1356} = 137$$

Onitsha South Local Government Council

$$= n^2 = \frac{\sum(x \cdot y)}{N}$$

$$n^2 = \frac{478 \cdot 309}{1356} = 109$$

Orumba South Local Government Council

$$= n^3 = \frac{\sum(x \cdot y)}{N}$$

$$n^3 = \frac{277 \cdot 309}{1356} = 63$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study is

$$\sum(n^1 + n^2 + n^3) = 137 + 109 + 63 = 309$$

Method of Data Analysis

The data generated from the instrument were analyzed using descriptive statistics precisely the

arithmetic mean and clearly represented in tables to demonstrate responses obtained from the target respondents. The respondents' responses were recorded in 5 point Likert scale of (SA) – Strongly Agreed, (A) Agreed, (U) – Undecided, (D) – Disagreed and (SD) – Strongly Disagreed.

Whereas

(SA) + (A) = Represent Accepted Response at 4.0 to 5

(U) + (D) + (SD) = Represent Rejected Response at 1.0 to 3.

Empirical Analysis and Discussion of Findings

The data collected via the instrument of data collection are represented in tabular form with brief analysis of respondents' responses to each research questions. Thereafter, discussion of findings is made sequel to the empirical verification.

Table 2. Does the Introduction of Transition Committee Down Played Bureaucratic Professionalism in Local Government Administration in Anambra State

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	Arithmetic Mean (\bar{X})	Remarks
1	Transition Committee members are appointed as the administrative Heads of the local government councils by the State Government	250	50	5	4	-	4.9	ACCEPTED
2	Transition Committee members are well educated to perform administrative functions of local Government Councils.	40	25	90	153	1	2.4	REJECTED
3	Transition Committee members possessed the requisite skills and training to Head local government councils in the state.	15	30	200	64	-	2.6	REJECTED
4	Contracts are awarded involving all the administrative heads of the departments and observe all due process before execution.	-	50	180	70	9	2.5	REJECTED
5	Transition Committee members arrogantly allocate revenue windows of the local government councils to themselves and to personal affiliated companies thereby running down the local government administration.	250	50	-	9	-	4.9	ACCEPTED

6	Transition Committee members with no academic background are assigned supervisors over the departments in the local government councils who ignorantly run down the administrative work.	190	100	10	-	9	4.7	ACCEPTED
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Source: Field Survey (2022)

From table 2 above, item 1 indicated that the respondents Accepted that the Transition Committee members are appointed as Administrative Heads of the local government councils by the state government. While items 2, 3, and 4 indicated serial rejection of the respondents that Transition Committee members are well educated to perform administrative functions of the local government councils, that they possessed requisite skills and training to head local government councils in the state and that contracts are awarded involving all

the administrative heads of departments and observed all due process before execution. While items 5 and 6 indicated that the respondents out rightly accepted that committee members arrogantly allocate revenue windows of the local government councils to themselves and to personal affiliated companies thereby running down the local government administration and that members with no academic background are assigned supervisors over the departments in the local government councils who ignorantly rescind the administrative work.

Table 3. Factors Attributed to Transition Committee that are Responsible for Low Performance of Local Government Administration in Anambra State

S/N	ITEMS	(SA) 5	(A) 4	(D) 3	(SD) 2	(U) 1	(\bar{X})	Remark
1	Poor academic background of the majority of the Transition Committee members is responsible for the low performance of the local government administration in Anambra State.	305	4	-	-	-	5	ACCEPTED
2	Imposition of Transition Committee on the local government councils has encouraged undivided loyalty to the governor and rubber stamped dispositions of the committee members and this has adversely affected productivity in local government councils	85	150	40	4	30	3.8	ACCEPTED
3	Irrational control of local government finances by the state government through the committee has adversely contributed to the poor execution of developmental projects at the grass root	100	100	55	34	20	3.2	ACCEPTED
4	Lack of administrative independence and seeking first the state government financial and administrative approvals for every intended statutory functions by the committee have impeded bureaucratic professionalism in the local government system in Anambra State.	250	45	2	9	3	4.8	ACCEPTED

Source: Field Survey (2022)

In table 3, it was observed from items 1, 2, 3 and 4 that all the respondents responded affirmatively to the question items. They accepted that poor academic background of majority of the committee members is responsible for the low performance of the local government administration in Anambra State. That imposition of committee members on the local government councils by the state government encouraged undivided loyalty to the governor and rubber stamped dispositions of the members which has adversely affected productivity in the local government councils. That irrational control of the local government finances by the state government through the committee has adversely contributed to the poor execution of developmental projects and lack of administrative independence and seeking first the state government financial and administrative approvals for every intended statutory functions by the committee have impeded bureaucratic professionalism in the local government administration in the state.

Discussion and Analysis of Findings

From the study the following findings were discovered;

- The introduction of Transition Committee into the local government administration has drastically weakened bureaucratic professionalism in the local government administration in Anambra State.
- The nature of the operation of Transition Committee has succeeded in encouraging total loss of financial and administrative independence of the local government not just as a third tier of the government but also as a bureaucratic organization. Under bureaucratic organization, it is expected to have clear channels of communication and defined statutory functions within the administrative structure. But here we have a situation where every action of the local government must first receive an approval from the state government before such action can be executed thereby defeating the very essence of

the constitutional establishment of the local government in Nigeria.

- The basis for which members of the Transition Committee are appointed has encouraged the recruitment of personalities with poor academic background and complete lack of requisite bureaucratic skills and experience for effective administration of the local government. And this has hampered bureaucratic professionalism in the local government administration in Anambra State.
- Lastly, lack of education of the Committee members, irrational control of the local government finances by the state government, and the committee members being routine subordinates and operating at the mercy of the Governor are all factors that have dampened the performance of the local government and has encouraged administrative rascality and bureaucratic ignorance in the local government councils in Anambra State.

Conclusion

In line with these findings, it has become imperative to conclude that the introduction of Transition Committee in the local government administration has frustrated bureaucratic professionalism in local government. The operation of Transition Committee in the local government has made mockery of local government administration as a bureaucratic organization and as such should be abrogated.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the researcher is emboldened to recommend as follows:

1. Transition Committee is an aberration to any bureaucratic organization particularly when its life span is beyond three months. Therefore, it is recommended that the committee be rescinded and election of the local government councils be conducted otherwise Local Government Heads of Administration should be

encouraged to be at the Head of affairs of the local government administration.

2. Also, it is recommended that in the event of setting up any fugacious administrative committee in the interim, a bureaucrat should be made to Head such committee. This will aide effective administrative performance in the local government.

Finally, the state government should spare the local government councils some space of control of their finances and administration. Administrative and financial autonomy are what guarantee bureaucratic professionalism at the local government councils and not applying for state government's approval for every intended action at the local government.

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